

Alternative Relativity

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Abstract: In addition to generating gravitational attraction, a gravitational field can also generate gravitational repulsion. Between objects, there exists not only universal gravitation but also universal repulsion. Universal repulsion is exactly dark energy. Whether an object is subjected to gravitational attraction or repulsion is determined by the velocity difference between the gravitational field and the object in the same or opposite direction. The gravitational field travels at the speed of light. Only when a gravitational field passes through another object can that object be affected by the acceleration of the gravitational field. Beyond our Big Bang universe, there are other Big Bang universes. The universe was born from a Big Bang and will be destroyed in a Big Collision. The gravitational field is a medium. In regions with stronger gravitational fields, light and electrons propagate more slowly. Because the speed of light and electrons slows down in a gravitational field, the time measured by atomic clocks also slows down. Gravitational fields of different intensities can refract light and electrons. When a particle moves at high speed, the frequency of its internal structure slows down, rather than time slowing down.

Keywords: Modified gravity; Dark matter; Dark energy; Cosmology; Gravitational wave; Relativity

I. Introduction

Modern physics holds that the universe originated from a Big Bang. I call this the Big Bang universe. What would you see if you traveled to the edge of the Big Bang universe and beyond? What would you see if you went back 13.8 billion years?

The universe is thought to have originated from a Big Bang about 13.8 billion years ago. Modern physics suggests there was no time before the Big Bang. If there was no time before the Big Bang, then the singularity could have exploded at any moment, so why exactly 13.8 billion years ago?

If you could travel back in time to before the Big Bang, to 13.8 billion years ago, what would you see?

Why is dark energy about twice as abundant as matter (including dark matter) in the universe, yet within a single galaxy, matter (including dark matter) is hundreds of

thousands of times more abundant than dark energy?

What existed before the birth of the universe?

What lies outside the universe?

Why does dark energy appear to increase out of nothing?

II. Current mainstream scientists' estimated values for dark matter and dark energy

The observable part of the universe is composed of approximately 4.9% visible matter (matter that makes up stars, planets, gas, and dust) or "baryons", 26.8% dark matter, and 68.3% dark energy.

III. Variation of acceleration with velocity difference

The acceleration of an object due to a field depends on the same-direction or opposite-direction velocity difference between the field and the object, and the magnitude of the field. The acceleration efficiency of the object is greatest when the same-direction or opposite-direction velocity difference between the field and the object reaches the speed of light, rather than the object's mass increasing with its velocity. The speed of electromagnetic waves, electromagnetic fields, and gravitational fields is the speed of light in a vacuum. A gravitational field is a medium.

The formula for acceleration under a field is as follows:

$$a = A \sqrt{1 - \left(\frac{V - c}{c}\right)^2}$$

Here, a is the acceleration of the object when moving under the influence of the field. A is the acceleration of the object when stationary under the influence of the field. c is the speed of light. V is the same-direction or opposite-direction velocity difference between the object and the field. The speed of gravitational, electric, and magnetic fields is the speed of light in a vacuum. A gravitational field is a medium.

IV. Formula for the effect of a gravitational field on an object

$$a = \sqrt{1 - \left(\frac{V - c}{c}\right)^2} (1 + \gamma R) \frac{Gm}{R^2} \cos \frac{\pi V}{c}$$

Here, a is the acceleration of the object under the influence of the gravitational field. m is the mass of the object emitting the gravitational field. G is the gravitational constant. R is the distance from the center of mass of the object emitting the gravitational field. V is the same-direction or opposite-direction velocity difference between the object and

the gravitational field. y is a constant. π is pi. c is the speed of light.

When $0 < V < 0.5c$, the object experiences a repulsive force. When $0.5c < V < 1.5c$, the object experiences an attractive force. When $V = 0.5c$, the object experiences no force. When $V = 0$, the object experiences no force. When $V = 1.5c$, the object experiences no force. When $V = 2c$, the object experiences no force. When $1.5c < V < 2c$, the object experiences a repulsive force.

V. Birth and demise of the universe

Beyond the Big Bang universe, there are countless other Big Bang universes, all of which collide with one another. After a collision, a nucleus forms, which absorbs matter from surrounding universes, growing larger and larger. Once the nucleus has absorbed sufficient matter, it undergoes a massive explosion, giving birth to a new universe.

VI. Propagation laws of light and electrons in a gravitational field

When light and electrons propagate through the same medium, the denser the medium, the slower they travel. A gravitational field is also a medium; similarly, the stronger the gravitational field, the slower light and electrons travel. It is not that time slows down in stronger gravitational fields, but rather the speed of light and electrons. Gravitational waves travel at the same speed as the gravitational field. In a gravitational field, light travels more slowly than gravitational waves, so gravitational wave detectors can detect waves before light does. Taking the GW170817 event as an example, gravitational waves were detected 1.7 seconds before light. Light and electrons are refracted when passing through gravitational fields of different intensities. Because photons and electrons slow down in a gravitational field, the frequency measured by an atomic clock in a stronger gravitational field is slower, and thus the time measured by the atomic clock is slower. It is not that time itself slows down in a stronger gravitational field.

$$n = \left(\frac{Gm}{r^2} - \frac{Gm}{R^2} \right) x$$

$$v = \frac{V}{\left(\frac{Gm}{r^2} - \frac{Gm}{R^2} \right) x}$$

$$f = \frac{F}{\left(\frac{Gm}{r^2} - \frac{Gm}{R^2} \right) b}$$

Here, R and r are the distances from the gravitational field source for photons or electrons traveling at velocities V and v , respectively. V is the speed of the

electron or photon farther from the source, v is their speed closer to the source, G is the gravitational constant, x is the refraction constant, m is the mass of the celestial body emitting the gravitational field, n is the refractive index of light and electrons in the gravitational field, f is the atomic frequency closer to the source, F is the atomic frequency farther from the source, and b is the atomic frequency constant.

VII. Frequency of Particles in High-Speed Motion

When a particle moves at high speed, the frequency of its internal structure slows down. It is not that time itself slows down at high speeds. Examples include atomic frequency and particle decay rates.

$$f = F \sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}}$$

f is the frequency of the particle when its speed is v . F is the frequency of the particle when stationary. v is the speed of the particle. c is the speed of light.

VIII. Conclusion

Gravity, dark matter, and dark energy are all manifestations of the gravitational field. Dark energy is essentially the repulsive force generated by the gravitational field. Dark matter arises from the attractive force generated by the gravitational field. The gravitational field is a medium. In regions with stronger gravitational fields, light and electrons propagate more slowly. Gravitational fields of different intensities can refract light and electrons. In a stronger gravitational field, the atomic frequency slows down, rather than time slowing down. For particles moving at high speed, it is the internal frequency of the particle that slows down, not time itself.

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替代相对论

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摘要：引力场除了产生引力还能产生斥力。物体之间除了存在万有引力，还存在万有斥力。万有斥力就是暗能量。引力场和物体的同向或反向的速度差决定物体受到的是引力还是斥力。引力场的速度是光速。引力场要穿过其他物体时，其他物体才能受到引力场加速度。大爆炸宇宙之外还有大爆炸宇宙，宇宙诞生于大爆炸，毁灭于大碰撞。引力场是一种介质。引力场越强的区域光和电子传播得越慢。因为在引力场中光和电子速度变慢，所以由原子钟测得的时间也就变慢。不同强度的引力场能让光和电子折射。粒子在高速运动时粒子内部结构频率会变慢。而不是时间变慢。

关键词：修正引力；暗物质；暗能量；宇宙学；引力波；相对论

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一、引言

现代物理学认为宇宙起源一次大爆炸。我把这个宇宙叫做大爆炸宇宙。你来到了大爆炸宇宙的边缘以外你会看到什么？你回到 138 亿年前你又能看到什么？

宇宙大概起源于 138 亿年前的一次大爆炸，现代物理学认为宇宙大爆炸之前是没有时间的。如果宇宙大爆炸之前是没有时间的，那奇点随时爆炸都可以，可是为什么是 138 亿年前？

当你穿梭飞行回到宇宙大爆炸之前，回到 138 亿年前 你会看到什么？

为什么暗能量在宇宙中大约是物质（包括暗物质）2 倍多。但是在一个星系中的物质（包括暗物质）是暗能量的数十万倍？

宇宙诞生前是是什么？

宇宙之外是什么？

暗能量为什么会凭空增加？

二、目前全球主流科学家对暗物质和暗能量的推测值

人类所观察到的部分宇宙的物件大约是由 4.9% 的可见物质（构成恒星、行星、气体和尘埃的物质）或“重子”，26.8% 的暗物质和 68.3% 的暗能量构成。^[1]

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三、加速度随速度差的变化效率。

物体受到场的加速度取决于靠场与物体同向或反向的速度差和场的量。场与物体同向或反向的速度差在光速时物体受到的加速度效率最大，而不是物体速度越大质量就越大。电磁波，电磁场，引力场的速度为无介质中的光速。引力场是一种介质。

场作用下加速度公式如下

$$a = A \sqrt{1 - \left(\frac{V - c}{c}\right)^2}$$

a 是物体运动时受到场产生的加速度。A是物体静止时受到场产生的加速度。c是光速。V是物体和场的同向或反向的速度差。引力场，电场和磁场的速度是无介质中的光速。引力场是一种介质。

四、引力场对物体的作用公式如下

$$a = \sqrt{1 - \left(\frac{V - c}{c}\right)^2} (1 + \gamma R) \frac{Gm}{R^2} \cos \frac{\pi V}{c}$$

a 是物体运动时受到的引力场作用的加速度。m是发射引力场物体的质量。G是万有引力常数。R是距离发出引力场物体质心的距离。V是物体和引力场的同向或反向的速度差。y是常数。 π 是圆周率。c是光速。

$0 < V < 0.5c$ 时物体受到的是排斥力， $0.5c < V < 1.5c$ 时物体受到的是吸引力。 $V = 0.5c$ 时物体不受力， $V = 0$ 时物体不受力， $V = 1.5c$ 时物体不受力。 $V = 2c$ 时物体不受力。 $1.5c < V < 2c$ 时物体受排斥力

五、宇宙的诞生与消亡

大爆炸宇宙之外还有无数的大爆炸宇宙，这些宇宙都会相互碰撞。碰撞之后形成一个核，这个核吸收周围宇宙的物质，然后越吸越多。等核吸收了足够的物质之后，核会发生大爆炸形成新的宇宙。

六、光和电子在引力场中的传播规律

光和电子传播时，同一种介质中密度越大，光和电子传播得越慢；引力场也是一种介质，同理引力场越强的区域光和电子传播得越慢；而不是引力场越强的区域时间越慢。引力波的速度和引力场一样。在引力场中光比引力波传播得更慢，所以引力波探测器比光更先探测到。以GW170817事件为例，引力波比光提前1.7秒探测到。光和电子在不同强度的引力场中会发生折射。由于光子和电子在引力场中速度变慢，所以原子在越强的引力场中测的原子频率也就越慢，原子钟的测得的时间就越慢。而不是引力场越强时间越慢。

$$n = \left(\frac{Gm}{r^2} - \frac{Gm}{R^2} \right) x$$

$$v = \frac{V}{\left(\frac{Gm}{r^2} - \frac{Gm}{R^2} \right) x}$$

$$f = \frac{F}{\left(\frac{Gm}{r^2} - \frac{Gm}{R^2} \right) b}$$

R 和 r 分别是 V 和 v 速度下的光子或电子距离引力场源路程。V 是离引力场源更远距离的电子和光子速度，v 是离引力场源更近距离的电子和光子速度，G 是万有引力常数，x 是折射常数，m 是发出引力场天体的质量。n 是光和电子在引力场中的折射率。f 是原子离引力场源更近的频率。F 是原子离引力场源更远的频率。b 是原子频率常数。

七、粒子在高速运动时的频率

粒子在高速运动时粒子内部结构频率会减慢，并不是高速运动下时间变慢。比如原子频率，粒子衰变速度。

$$f = F \sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}}$$

f 是粒子速度为 v 时的频率，F 是粒子速度静止时频率，v 是粒子的速度，c 是光速

八、结束语

引力，暗物质，暗能量都是引力场的个反应。暗能量其实就是引力场产生的排斥力。暗物质来自引力场产生的吸引力。引力场是一种介质。引力场越强的区域光和电子传播得越慢。不同强度的引力场能让光和电子折射。在越强的引力场下，原子频率越慢，而不是时间变慢。高速运动的粒子，是粒子内部的频率减慢，而不是时间变慢。

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